

INSTITUTIONAL STAFFING CAPACITY AND INTERNAL EFFICIENCY OF TECHNICAL TRAINING INSTITUTIONS IN BUNGOMA COUNTY, KENYA

Maximilla Wakoli¹ⁱ,

Julius Maiyo²,

Alice Limo³

¹Doctoral Student,
Department of Educational Management
and Foundations of Education,
University of Eldoret,
Kenya

²Ass. Prof,
Department of Educational Foundation,
Planning and Management, Kibabii University,
Kenya

³PhD, Lecturer,
Department of Educational Management and
Foundations of Education, University of Eldoret,
Kenya

Abstract:

This paper investigates how institutional staffing processes influence internal efficiency of public technical training institutions in the county of Bungoma, Kenya. The study was guided by resource dependence theory. The target population involved public TTIs tutors, principals of the TTIs and resource mobilisation officers in the four institutions located in the county of Bungoma; Sangalo Institute of Science and Technology, Kisiwa, Matili and Musakasa Technical Training Institutes. The study adopted mixed method research which was cross-sectional in nature. The data collection instruments involved use of questionnaires, interview schedules and document checklist. Qualitative data was transcribed and presented in verbatim with the use of content analysis method. Quantitative data analysis was done using descriptive (frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviation) and inferential (Multiple Linear Regression) statistics. The results in Table 4.5 show that there exist a moderate positive relationship ($r=0.473$ and $p=0.00$) between institutional staffing capacity at the four public TTIs in Bungoma county. The relationship appears to be significant at 99% confidence level. The study recommends that there is need for public TTIs to consider collaborating with other institutions within and outside the country for benchmarking of staff exchange

ⁱ Correspondence: maximillawakoli@gmail.com

programmes that could be important in improving skills and knowledge among the staff.

Keywords: institutional staffing, resource mobilisation, internal, efficiency

1. Introduction

Internal efficiency is the extent to which resources made available to the educational system are being used to achieve the objectives for which the educational system has been set up. In this regard, the input into the system and the output from it need to be measured (Yang, 2014). The inputs include classroom, teachers, furniture, textbooks, etc. and all these can be quantified as the cost per student per year. Thus, the input has to be in terms of student years. The outputs of the educational system are the graduates from that system (Ithuta, 2014). The implication here is that there should be optimum enrolment of students in educational institutions so that the resources can be fully utilised. Khamala (2012) suggests that the resources used in education should be properly utilized by the enrolled number of students so that they can reap maximum from them and hence a given educational institution realizing internal efficiency. This paper looked at how inputs of internal efficiency; institutional staffing influenced internal efficiency in public technical institutions in Bungoma County, Kenya.

Institutional staff capacity is also critical for internal efficiency in the education system. The need of training and retraining is important in order to develop innovative TTI teachers (Mohaffyza, Sukri & Ahmad, 2015). In Ethiopia, Sime (2014) found out that there was absence of training need assessment, lack of adequate and relevant labour market information, weak provision of vocational guidance service, concentrating on a restricted range of training programs, makes TTIs system inefficient and irresponsive to labour market needs. This shows that inadequate human resource provision and professional development affect internal efficiency of TTIs. In Kenya, Ferej, Kitainge and Ooko (2012) observed that there was need for continuous reform and upgrading of the skills that teachers possess, that the facilities for training should be as close and similar to the facilities found at the workplace, and that the institution – industry link should be made more mutually beneficial. This research will investigate human resource mobilization in Bungoma County, Kenya. Sang, Muthaa and Mbugua (2012) said that technical education is necessary if Kenya is to industrialize by the year 2030. Technical training institutions in Kenya are governed by Technical and Vocational Education and Training Act of (2013). The TVET Act provides the establishment of TVET authority that provide for the governance and management of institutions offering technical and vocational education and training; to provide for coordinated assessment, examination and certification; to institute a mechanism for promoting access and equity in training; to assure standards, quality and relevance; and for connected purposes. The establishment of this body has brought sanity in the way public and private institutions are run in Kenya.

2. Purpose of the Study

Implementation of TVET curriculum has not been yielding the expected outcome and results in terms of realising graduates who are beneficial to the job market. Muthima (2015) observed that TVET in Kenya is yet to produce adequate and skilled middle level human resource required to meet the demands for national development with the anticipated ratio of 1:3:12:60 for technologists, technicians, crafts persons and artisans respectively. Past research shows that provision of technical education faces critical challenges relating to inadequate human resource. Research on establishing how public TTIs are responding to institutional staffing capacity on internal efficiency remains inadequate. Therefore this paper looked at human resource mobilisation strategies influence internal efficiency of public TTIs in Bungoma County.

2.1 Objective of the Study

To determine institutional staffing capacity and internal efficiency of technical training institutions in Bungoma County.

2.2 Hypothesis for the Study

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between institutional staffing capacity and internal efficiency of technical training institutions in Bungoma County.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

This research study was guided by Resource Dependence Theory (RDT) advanced by Pfeffer and Salancik (1978). According to Odundo and Rambo (2013), the theory originated in the 1970 through the publication of 'external control of organisation: a resource dependence perspective by Pfeffer and Salancik (1978). RDT is underpinned by the tenet that resources are key to organisation success and that access and control over resources is a basis of power. It is the study of how resources such as raw materials of organisation affect the behaviour of organisation. Resource dependence theory is the study of how resources in organisations affect the behaviour of organisation. The resources in an organisation are important tenets of strategic and tactical management of any institution. This theory is used to explain the behaviour of TTIs to mobilise additional human resources to run their programmes that are aimed at improving quality of Technical education.

3. Literature Review

Human resources are the people who constitute the workforce in an organization (Abdulkareem, Fasasi & Akinnubi, 2011). The quality of staff in TVET institutions affects the internal efficiency (Yang, 2014). The characteristics that are related with quality of staff include staff attitude, qualification, experience, motivation, classroom management and their interaction with students' in the institution. In planning the quality of education and training, it is obvious that teachers are probably the most vital

component of the entire education process (Kitui, 2015). Abuel-Ealer (2012) note that how they are prepared for teaching is a critical indicator of education quality given that good teacher training should deal with aspects like academic qualifications, pedagogical training, experience, in-service training and professional development. Therefore, Abuel-Ealer concluded that educational institutions should have sufficient and highly qualified teachers. Rahman, Kim and Pei (2015) said that income generation activities have been acquainted among public higher education institutions (HEIs) in Malaysia. Various factors that brought to insufficient of funding caused Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to seek for additional income as to support the operation expenses. Financial sustainability issues made up the significant impact towards HEIs. This research employed qualitative method by conducting interviews as a medium to provide insights to researcher. Then, the interviews data were analysed using the interactive model. The results pointed out that the main income generation activities originated from the research and consultancy whilst commercialization contributed the most significant income towards university. As a conclusion, the income which generated by the academic staffs is at utmost importance to the development and sustainability of a university. Perhaps this research is significant to those who are concerning on the issues of income generating activities arisen among academic staffs. Through the results gained, certain parties may be known to the root of problems and then, solve it. It will eventually help the university to get a better way in order to attain the optimal results in income generation.

Investing in training leads to acquisition of skills that raise labour productivity and they require to be employable or to create their own to allow widespread use of existing technology, in addition training allows promotion of new technological development. Globalization places a lot of pressure on not only the economies but also the enterprises and individuals to become competitive. Higher level of skills is therefore a core factor in enhancing and enabling the necessary response. Training is therefore required continuously throughout working life to enhance employability of the individual and collectively the flexibility of the workforce. This means that training should equip people with skills and competences jobs (Kamau, 2013). However, teachers in Vocational Education and Training Institutions rarely go for in-service trainings, lack a scheme of service and earned little salaries hence had low morale. The few qualified teachers left the profession due to low salaries, difficult working conditions and insufficient professional support (Bourgonje & Tramp, 2011).

Tutors in TVET institutions are a critical component of the training requirements. The R.O.K. (2005) emphasizes on the need for adequate staff-ing for the effective education at all levels of training. An item in the H.O.D questionnaire sought to inquire on the adequacy of trainers in the departments. Sang et al. (2011) found out that majority of the respondents said that the trainers were not adequate while others respondents indicated that the trainers were adequate to implement the training duties in the department. The shortage of trainers therefore emerged as one of the challenges facing T.T.Is in Kenya. The trainers' level of qualification is critical in determining the efficiency of the training process. Aduda (2003) observes that the trainer should possess

higher qualification to effectively execute the training duties. The study sought information on the academic qualifications of T.T.I trainers.

Pitan (2012) examined the relationship between human resource utilization and internal efficiency of some secondary schools in Ibadan North Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria. The study was carried out using a descriptive survey design, while purposive sampling technique was adopted for selecting eight (8) out of 22 public secondary schools in the local government area of the state. Results showed that a significant positive relationship existed between student-teacher ratio (STR) and wastage ratio; however, there was no significant relationship between teacher quality (in terms of qualification), teachers' workload and wastage ratio respectively. Using the input-output analysis of the sampled schools, it was established that there was a highly positive relationship between resource utilization and internal efficiency of the school system. The performance of students in public examination revealed that there were lots of wastages (students' failure) in the system, making the system inefficient.

Butare (2004) noted that many employed Rwandans wish to pursue further studies to advance their professional careers but cannot have time off their jobs to engage in lengthy professional study programmes. In response to this need, KIST established the Department of Part-Time Studies, which has well over one thousand self-sponsored evening students pursuing degree and diploma courses under the Faculties of Management and Technology. In addition, the institute occasionally offers on demand short courses such as basic computer courses, ACCA, CISCO and Microsoft certified programmes. Part-time study programmes have responded positively to community needs at no extra cost to the institute because they are priced at market rates and are therefore self-sustaining. In Eritrea, Woldu (2017) examined the role of school principal in facilitating change in teaching-learning process. Moreover, it has focused on the main roles of principal in implementing LCIP. The research employed both quantitative and qualitative methods. The study used a random sample of 62 teachers from a purposefully selected five junior schools in Asmara. The results of the study revealed that teachers believe that the principals in junior schools in Asmara have been facilitating implementation of the change introduced by the Ministry of Education in LCIP. They believe that principals have been striving on facilitating the change through exerting the proper leadership style, provision and mobilization of resources, playing supervisory role, enhancing the provision of school based training and development programs and creating appropriate communication channels. The research was done in Eritrea junior schools while this research was conducted in Kenya TTIs.

Sang et al. (2011) found out that most of the trainers were either diploma holders or first-degree holders in each case. About less than 25% of the trainers were said to have higher diploma and masters respectively. The study established that majority of the trainers were either diploma holders or first degree graduates. This is despite the fact that most T.T.I graduates left the institutions with a diploma qualification. It is therefore clear that the T.T.Is are poorly staffed with highly skilled instructors, making the quality of training low. To address low number of trainers, majority of the respondents (66.7%) indicated that the situation was managed by hiring part time

teachers, whereas 21.2% of the respondents identified multi-grade teaching as a solution. 3.0% of the respondents indicated that trainees were left to learn on their own. The study established the T.T.Is resulted to desperate moves in managing staff shortages that included the hiring of part-time lecturers as the most commonly used option. Multi-grade teaching was used as an option where the trainers combined trainees taking similar units though at different levels into the same classroom, workshops or laboratories.

Kitui (2015) assessed the availability and quality of teachers in the youth polytechnics that is, the number of teachers available, their qualifications and how often they attend programmes like in-service induction courses. From the results, 92.8% of trainee respondents and 97.3% of the managers agreed that youth polytechnics did not have enough trained and qualified teachers. Even the few available teachers were mainly of low qualifications at the minimal grade of certificate. Kibet, Zhimin and Chelagat (2013) study was to review and analyze the resources needs and sources of resources and level of training and capacity building in resource mobilization in Kenyan private chartered universities. The study employed a descriptive survey research design. Purposeful sampling technique was used to select 63 respondents (staff) from three private universities within Nakuru town. Data was collected by use of questionnaires. Study findings showed that: training and capacity-building efforts on resource mobilization are yet to have a significant impact on resource mobilization efforts; students were the main source of resources for the private universities and tuition fees formed the bulk of the resources mobilized by private universities; regular awareness, training and capacity-building in resource mobilization among the staff; empowerment of university campuses in order to mobilize as many resources. Ferej et al. (2012) established that each year the government provides some funds to each TVET institution to meet its running costs related to payment of salaries. Instructors who are registered with the Teachers Service Commission (TSC) are paid their salaries which are also derived from national annual budget. Some institutions, however, hire teachers through the institutions management boards where they have needs to meet and an instructor not posted by the TSC. It is not known whether TTIs in Bungoma County hire extra teachers to manage the workload that existing teachers are facing.

3. Materials and Methods

This study was conducted in Bungoma County Kenya. This research used a mixed method research methodology. Mixed-methods approach focuses on data collection and analysis mixing with both qualitative and quantitative data sources in one study or in a series of studies (Al-Dossary, 2008). The study adopted a descriptive survey design that incorporated qualitative and quantitative aspects. The target population for this study involved four TTIs located in Bungoma County, which are Sang'alo Institute of Science and Technology, Kisiwa Technical Training Institute, Musakasa Technical Training Institute and Matili Technical Training Institute. The respondents from these four TTIs included; four principals of TTIs, 16 managers in charge of resource

mobilisation activities and 239 tutors. The final sample size consisted of 4 principals from TTIs, 16 resource mobilisation managers and 150 tutors as respondents for the study. The primary data was collected through questionnaire, interview of respondents and observation checklists. Quantitative data were analysed using descriptive and inferential methods. Inferential method includes Pearson Product Correlation and Descriptive ones were frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviation. The hypothesis was tested at 95.0% confidence level.

3.1 Results and Discussion

To deliver quality and effective Technical education, adequate human resource (teaching and non-teaching) have to be available. The objective of this study sought to determine institutional staffing capacity and its relation with internal efficiency of public TTIs in Bungoma County. Therefore, tutors were asked to rate the frequency to which institutional staffing capacity methods was applied in their colleges using the following scale: never (1), rarely (2), sometimes (3), often (4) and always (5). The findings are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Institutional Staffing Capacity of TTIs in Bungoma County

Staffing capacity	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always	Mean	SD
Our institution ensures that qualified staff are recruited to ensure quality TVET education	0 (0.0%)	6 (4.6%)	30 (23.1%)	44 (33.8%)	50 (38.5%)	4.0615	.89576
Our institution invests in continuous professional development for all staff to increase their competencies towards quality service delivery	7 (5.4%)	36 (27.7%)	62 (47.7%)	17 (13.1%)	8 (6.2%)	2.8692	.92668
The institution has ensured that there is adequate human resource to reduce workload	2 (1.5%)	31 (23.8%)	51 (39.2%)	29 (22.3%)	17 (13.1%)	3.2154	1.00375
There is good scheme of service for all members staff in this institution to motivate and retain them	9 (6.9%)	46 (35.4%)	42 (32.3%)	22 (16.9%)	11 (8.5%)	2.8462	1.05992
Our institution partners with other institution in exchange programmes to improve standards of teaching	7 (5.4%)	57 (43.8%)	44 (33.8%)	13 (10.0%)	9 (6.9%)	2.6923	.97126
The institution partners with industry to bridge the gap between industry and research among our graduates	4 (3.1%)	21 (16.2%)	42 (32.3%)	39 (30.0%)	24 (18.5%)	3.4462	1.06430
The resource mobilisation is a teamwork process to ensure attainment of institutional goals	10 (7.7%)	53 (40.8%)	33 (25.4%)	15 (11.5%)	19 (14.6%)	2.8462	1.18427
All staff members are better remunerated to increase their productivity	14 (10.8%)	59 (45.4%)	44 (33.8%)	7 (5.4%)	6 (4.6%)	2.4769	.92523
Our institution offers scholarships for staff wishing to go for further studies to improve their competitiveness	39 (30.0%)	63 (48.5%)	19 (14.6%)	7 (5.4%)	2 (1.5%)	2.0000	.89789
Our institution hires part-time staff due to shortage of full time staff to address inefficiency	11 (8.5%)	29 (22.3%)	43 (33.1%)	23 (17.7%)	24 (18.5%)	3.1692	1.19520
Composite scores						2.9623	1.01243

Research findings shows in Table 1 that 50 (38.5%) agreed that their institution always ensured that qualified staff were recruited for the purpose of providing quality TVET education to students, 44 (33.8%) said that their institution often ensured, 30 (23.1%) sometime ensured while 6 (4.6%) said that they rarely ensured that. Computed descriptive statistics values ($M=4.06$ and $SD=0.89$) shows that all the four institutions often ensured that qualified and competent teaching and non-teaching staff are employed for the purpose of ensuring teaching staff meet the minimum requirements required to teach in those institutions. When unqualified people are given opportunities to work, the institutions may fail to achieve quality education, as most of them cannot deliver the demands that their jobs entail. These results were also confirmed by Esongo (2017) who established that availability of qualified manpower in schools (with a mean value of 2.70) and the possession of adequate experience and appropriate pre-service training to promote competency based teaching (with a mean value of 2.88) were moderate.

Secondly, research findings shows that 62 (47.7%) of respondents indicated that their institution sometimes invested in continuous professional development for all staff with the aim of improving their competencies and teaching pedagogies. The descriptive statistics ($M=2.86$ and $SD=0.92$) shows that the four TTIs do sometimes provide opportunities for Continuous Professional Development (CPD) for their teaching and non-teaching staff to increase their knowledge, skills and competencies. The study agrees with Haramoto (2015) research in Sudan that found out instructors in TTIs were not provided with in-service training. In addition, Esongo (2017) research found out that majority of the respondents were exposed to at most two short duration seminars (of a day or two) per academic year which was largely insufficient to go through the very demanding mastery of competency-based teaching approaches in Cameroon. This shows that most employees are not guaranteed opportunities for increasing knowledge and skills and which may affect their delivery of services to students in the institutions. This implies that employees' professional development is not valued at such in the public TTIs in Bungoma County.

Thirdly, research results show that only 51 (39.2%) of respondents agreed that their institution had ensured that there was adequate human resources in their schools to manage workload. The descriptive scores ($M=3.21$ and $SD=1.00$) suggests that this is an act that is conducted regularly in the institutions with the aim of ensuring that proper curriculum is provided to students. This could be because the institutions rely on TSC to provide them with adequate teaching staff that in some cases could take long before the requests are done. However, through internal mechanism, the institutions could cover the shortfall (human resource) through employment of BOM teachers and casuals from income generating projects that institutions undertake. In line with the study findings, Sang et al. (2011) established the T.T.Is resulted to desperate moves in managing staff shortages that included the hiring of part-time lecturers as the most commonly used option. Multi-grade teaching was used as an option where the trainers combined trainees taking similar units though at different levels into the same classroom, workshops or laboratories. In contrast to the study findings, Yang (2014)

established that major factors contributing to poor internal efficiency stated were high students'- section ratio and low number of teachers in schools. This implies that when there are no adequate human resources in schools, the internal efficiency is greatly affected.

When asked on whether scheme of services was improved from time to time for all members of the staff in the institution to motivate them and retain them in institutions, 9 (6.9%) said that was not there, 46 (35.4%) said it was rare, 42 (32.3%) said it sometimes happen, 22 (16.9%) indicated that it was often done and 11 (8.5%) said that it was always done. The result shows ($M=2.84$ and $SD=1.05$) that sometimes there is good scheme of services while in other instances, it is not there hence could result to staff turnover intentions. This implies that when employees are not provided with favourable scheme of services on regular basis, this could affect their job morale and motivation that could affect internal efficiency of the institutions in producing low quality and incompetent graduates. The findings coincides with Esongo (2017) research that showed that was inadequate incentives/rewards (like low salaries and remuneration) to promote competency-based teaching, lack of funding to run training seminars for teachers in schools to promote effective curriculum implementation.

On whether they collaborated with other institutions through exchange programmes for benchmarking purposes and improving standards of providing TVET curriculum, 7 (5.4%) said that they never, 57 (43.8%) said it is sometimes done, 44 (33.8%) said it is sometimes done, 13 (10.0%) said that it is often done and 9 (6.9%) said it is always done. This therefore shows that it is not a common practice ($M=2.69$ and $SD=0.97$) for the public TTIs in the study area to have staff exchange programmes with other institutions. Considering the importance of benchmarking in technical and vocational education, most of the institutions surveyed have not utilised this opportunity which would be significant in improving their internal efficiency levels. The importance of staff exchange programme is aimed at improving organisational learning process as best practices could be learnt from the partnering institutions. On the linkage between the colleges and industry to bridge the gap between what is taught theoretically in class and what happens in the field, 4 (3.1%) of tutors said that their institutions never partnered with industry, 21 (16.2%) rarely partnered with industry, 42 (32.3%) sometimes partnered with industry, 39 (30.0%) often partnered with industry and 24 (18.5%) always partnered with industry to bridge the gap that exists between industry and research which improves the success of their students in the job market. The result implies that most institutions sometimes ($M=3.44$ and $SD=1.06$) partner with industry to assist their students to apply the knowledge learnt in class to practical situation in the industry. This also explains why respondents earlier indicated that the success of students' rate in the job market is on average since institutions do not the burden of ensuring that they get and look for internship and attachment opportunities for their students in industry. This state of affairs may affect the achievement of internal efficiency goals in public TTIs.

When asked as to whether the process of resource mobilisation was all-inclusive to ensure attainment of institutional goals, 10 (7.7%) disagreed, 53 (40.8%) said that it is rarely done, 33 (25.4%) indicated that it was sometimes done, 15 (11.5%) said that this was often done and 19 (14.6%) said that this was a regular process in their institutions. The results therefore shows that sometimes ($M=2.84$ and $SD=1.18$), the public TTIs worked together with all staff to mobilise resources while in other instances they do not. This implies that the failure of staff development efforts to achieve their objective is because of school management partial involvement of all staff at different levels in the organisation. The study is different from Kibet et al. (2013) results that showed that a significant proportion of the private universities conducted awareness on resource mobilization at least monthly or did not at all. This implies that public institutions need to value the input of their members of staff when mobilising resources for the aim of attaining high internal efficiency scores. Research findings further showed that most 59 (45.4%) of tutors said that they members of staff are rarely better remunerated with the aim of increasing their productivity in the school. Results suggests that apart from the salary that tutors get form TSC, public TTIs in Bungoma County rarely remunerated their teaching and non-teaching staff. Lack of better remuneration of employees did affect their commitment level as some would even opt not to give their best when delivering their services to students. This in contrast with Awuour (2015) whose study revealed that nearly all the schools (96.7%) motivated their staff through awards, which were either monetary or material gifts. Prompt payment of salaries or any service. The result therefore shows disparity exists between secondary schools and tertiary institutions efforts in motivating staff. When members of staff are not motivated, their morale declines which later affects performance of students at the end of their module examinations.

To explain further the implication of the above findings, when member of staff in a technical and vocational institutions (TTIs) were not remunerated well, issues of absenteeism, transfers and turnover are common and this ultimately influences the internal efficiency of the said institutions. Research findings also show that most 63 (48.5%) of tutors said that their institutions rarely offered scholarships for staff who wished to go for further studies. This implies that scholarships opportunities are rare ($M=2.0$ and $SD=0.89$) in the four public TTIs from Bungoma County. This also explains why demographic data showed that most tutors were degree holders and few possessed masters degree. When institutions fail to look and provide for scholarships for further education for their staff, this may affect their knowledge and skills levels considering that the way instruction was done 30 years ago is different in this technological age hence making them not being in a position to compete with other established technical institutions within and outside the country. In some institutions, the researcher found out that there was skewed issuance of scholarships as those connected and related to management benefited than deserving members of staff therefore creating mistrust between the institutions management and members of staff. On the frequency to which the institutions hired part – time staff to address the shortage of full time staff to address issues of inefficiencies, 11 (8.5%) did not hire, 29

(22.3%) rarely hired, 43 (33.1%) sometimes hired, 23 (17.7%) often hired and only 24 (18.5%) said that their institutions hired. This shows that most institutions in the study area sometimes ($M=3.16$ and $SD=1.19$) hired part time workers to bridge the shortfall. This could be because of inadequate funding that the government provides to these technical institutions making them to utilise members of staff who are available.

However, as part of resource mobilisation strategy, institutions board of management may find ways through which they can generate additional revenue to support payment of casual workers who would improve internal efficiency of these institutions. Average scores shows that institutional staff mobilisation strategies were at times ($M=2.96$ and $SD=1.01$) conducted in the four public technical training institutions in Bungoma County. In line with the study findings, Kibet et al. (2013) he concluded that majority of the study respondents (staff) either did not attend capacity-building training on resource mobilization or did not attend the capacity-building sufficiently enough even if conducted by their institutions. Resource mobilisation managers were asked to give their views with regard to achievements made by their institutions in institutionalising staff capacity. Officer Number 16 had this to say:

“Improved staff numbers through hiring teaching staff on part time basis to easen-congested workload. At least one staff competently trained in a year.”

Another officer had to say this with regard to institutional staffing capacity in his or her college:

“Staffing capacity has been supported on the side of hiring but training and the institute has not supported staff development; the individual staff members have attained higher training and development on their own using their own resources.”

In addition, officer number two indicated the following:

“I have continued to hire required staff each time there is need. A good number of office leavers had an opportunity to go for training; I facilitated training of about thirty teachers in ICT.”

The above information from resource mobilisation managers confirms that institutional staffing happens in the four TTIs under consideration in this study. Staffing capacity has been supported on the side of hiring but training and the institute has not supported staff development; the individual staff members have attained higher training and development on their own using their own resources. In line with the study findings, Pitan (2012) established that the available human resources were well utilized, there was an increase in the level of internal efficiency of the school system. The research went further to determine the kind of relationship that existed between institutional staffing capacity efforts and internal efficiency through computation of Karl Pearson correlation statistics. The results of the analysis are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Relationship between Institutional Staffing Capacity and Internal Efficiency of TTIs

		Institutional staffing capacity	Internal efficiency
Institutional staffing capacity	Pearson Correlation	1	.473**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	130	130
Internal efficiency	Pearson Correlation	.473**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	130	130

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field data (2018).

The results show that there exist a moderate positive relationship ($r=0.473$ and $p=0.00$) between institutional staffing capacity at the four public TTIs in Bungoma county. The relationship appears to be significant at 99% confidence level. In agreement with the study findings, Abdulkareem, Fasasi and Akinnubi (2011) found out that significant relationship existed between human resources utilization and internal efficiency in the state-owned universities. The role of the lecturers cannot be underscored in teaching-learning process and in attainment of educational goals at the university level. This implies that continuous commitment by TTIs management to improve staffing capacity would results to increased internal efficiency levels. This implies more needs to be done by the institutions to mobilise human resources. Further, the tutors through open-ended questions were asked which other strategies their schools might use to mobilise human resources for improving internal efficiency of their schools. The tutors suggested that there is need for institutional administration to consider increasing the workshops in schools. Secondly, they suggested that their institutions should consider hiring casual workers to bridge human resource shortfall. Thirdly, they said that there is need for school management to promote good working conditions for all staff. There was also need for the college management to consider benchmarking with other Technical institutions for the staff to learn from what others are doing. Aspects of employee motivation; giving of incentives for all staff, recognition, promotion, sponsorship for further training and performance contracting were also mentioned as measures which the institutions may undertake to improve institutional staffing capacity aimed at improving internal efficiency.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

The study determined relationship between institutional staff capacity in public technical training institutions in Bungoma County. The principals noted that they have improved the capacity of teaching and non-teaching staff through working with TSC to raise the number of teaching staff and BOM to hire part time workers. However, they admitted that they are usually unable to provide continuous professional development programmes to the staff because of limited resources and funding. On their part, the tutors mentioned that in institutional staffing capacity, their schools only ensures that qualified members of staff are recruited only ($M=4.06$ and $SD=0.89$). On the least side,

the tutors reported that their institutions rarely ($M=2.0$ and 0.89) rarely offered scholarships and sponsorships opportunities for members of staff (academic and non-academic) who wished to pursue further studies. Abridged means revealed that institutional staffing capacity mobilisation efforts were at moderate level ($M=2.96$ and $SD=1.01$). This explains why the results showed that most employees were poorly remunerated. Computed correlation results showed that there existed an average degree level of association ($r=0.473$ and $p=0.001$) between institutional staffing capacity and internal efficiency of public technical training institutions in Bungoma County. This showed that more needs to be done by institutional management to improve the efforts of mobilising adequate human resources for improving internal efficiency of public TTIs. This meant that when staffing capacity is regularly done, internal efficiency objectives would be attained. To improve on institutional staffing capacity, there is need for public TTIs to consider collaborating with other institutions within and outside the country for benchmarking of staff exchange programmes that could be important in improving skills and knowledge among the staff. There is also need for staff members to be remunerated well to increase their productivity. Public TTIs should sponsor their staff for further studies through provision of scholarships to increase their knowledge and skills.

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